

LEGITIMATE INTERESTS OF MINORS FROM SINGLE-PARENT FAMILIES IN THE NEIGHBORHOOD

Musurmanova Sh.I.

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute
Senior teacher of the Department of Pedagogy

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Abstract. *In this article, the conflicts in dysfunctional families are expressed by the formation of ideas about values, norms, imaginations, views, norms of behavior in the spirituality of children of different ages in the family. Accordingly, the ways of eliminating the neglect and delinquency of minors will also change. However, cooperation between family and community organizations and law enforcement agencies remains the most appropriate measure in these cases.*

Keywords: *mahalla, society, incomplete family, values, parents, child, family, divorced family, entrepreneurship, smart woman, complex, functional, spouse, marriage.*

As long as there is a society, there will be a problem of working with children. One generation is replaced by a new one. Their achievements, shortcomings, offenses will also be unique. After all, as our Head of State stated, "The most honorable dream of any nation, of any person who is lucky enough to be a parent, has always been to bring up a healthy, well-rounded generation, to raise a person who is perfect in all aspects." [1]

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "Family is sacred for us. The sanctity is that, first of all, no matter where he works, no matter who he is, if he does not pay special attention to education in the family, atmosphere in the family, honesty in the family, attitude, education, there will never be results. That's why I pay a lot of attention to the education of my children. I have a special relationship with each of my children and grandchildren. I know the special character of each of my grandchildren, I know their dreams and desires." [2]

In most cases, the term "unsupervised" refers to children who are on the list of law enforcement officers, prone to drug and alcohol abuse, hooliganism, and theft. Such children resist pedagogic-psychological influences in the process of education, stubbornness, putting themselves above others, i.e. cases of non-observance of positive moral norms are clearly noticeable in their behavior.

The main reasons for the appearance of unsupervised and neglected children in the neighborhood and family are, first of all, the poor spiritual environment in the family, insufficient attention to the child's personality in the educational process in schools, boring and low-level classes, the same approach to all children, the imperfection of their socio-pedagogical-psychological abilities, individual and such as not paying attention to their intellectual capabilities. The presence of hatred, rudeness, insufficient childhood, and improper setting of the goal towards the child of a single-parent family in the neighborhood and educational institution lead to the increase of street children.

Such vices encourage the child of a single-parent family to break the law and create an opportunity for the emergence of negative mistakes such as drug addiction. As a result, there is a risk of ruining future plans for a child of a single-parent family, children who have turned away from education and social activity prefer to establish contact with "friends" they made from bad circles and "save" from other people, rather than devoting their future, dreams and hopes to school

and peer activities. seeks, as a result of his pursuit of "professional" groups, when he falls into a group of children with unhealthy behavior, he adapts to them.

There is nothing easier than slapping, cursing, or threatening a child who steals sweets or misbehaves in the market. It is more difficult to reverse it, to find out why it is in this situation and to correct it. Therefore, it is necessary to be patient in these matters and continuously take measures to correct the child of an incomplete family, father or mother, chairman of the community assembly, preventive (senior) inspector, assistant to the governor, women's activist, youth leader, as well as "Aqila members of the women's movement and other officials are required.

Taking into account that most of the children of unsupervised and neglected single-parent families are teenagers, it is necessary to highlight the effective services of law enforcement agencies. [3] They are doing a good job of finding such children, returning them to their parents, and transferring them to state care if the parents themselves need education.

Minors - who are they? Why are they named that way? The word "didn't" itself can explain this sentence.

A minor is a person under the age of eighteen. Preventing delinquency and delinquency among them is a necessary activity among today's teenagers. Social, legal, medical and other measures, aimed at identifying and eliminating the reasons and conditions that allow minors to be unsupervised, neglected, commit crimes or other anti-social behavior, together with individual preventive work should be applied.

A minor child from a single-parent family may be in a very dangerous situation socially. Everyone is concerned that due to lack of control or neglect, he is in a condition that does not meet the requirements for his life or health, or does not meet the requirements of his provision, upbringing and education, or that he is under the influence of a group that commits crimes or other anti-social behavior. If we analyze this situation in depth, these children often turn out to be children of incomplete families.

Children of single-parent families in neighborhoods who regularly consume alcohol, drugs, psychotropic or other psychoactive substances, engage in prostitution, begging, as well as those who commit other actions that violate the rights, freedoms and legal interests of other citizens are considered the most dangerous group.

The new version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was adopted by popular vote in the referendum of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 30, 2023. Chapter XIV of the new Constitution is dedicated to the protection of the rights and interests of the family, children and young people. neighborhood officials are required to act in all-round support for children. Including,

Article 76:

The family is the main link of the society and it is protected by the society and the state. The state creates social, economic, legal and other conditions for the full development of the family.

Article 78:

It is the responsibility of the state to ensure and protect the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the child, to create the best conditions for his full physical, mental and cultural development.

Motherhood, fatherhood and childhood are protected by the state.

The state and society take care of the formation of children and young people's loyalty to national and universal values, pride in their country and the rich cultural heritage of the people, feelings of patriotism and love for the Motherland.

Article 79:

The state ensures the protection of personal, political, economic, social, cultural and environmental rights of young people, encourages their active participation in the life of society and the state.

The state creates conditions for the formation and development of young people intellectually, creatively, physically and morally, for the realization of their rights to education, health care, housing, employment, employment and recreation.

Article 80:

The adopted articles of this constitution not only protect the child, but also define their rights and duties.

Usually, when we say the rights of minors, we understand their material provision. This is only partly true. In article 64 of our dictionary, equal importance is given not only to raising a child, but also to education. This means realizing the moral rights of children in all families.

Several recommendations can be noted to prevent neglect and delinquency among children with problems in single-parent families in the neighborhoods:

1. Controlling the child, taking into account the location of the neighborhood, the presence of markets, entertainment avenues in the neighborhood creates a number of problems in keeping the child under control and conducting practical work on the offense.

Here it should be noted that neighborhoods are composed of multi-story buildings, courtyards, cottages, field yards, villages, farms. As our national traditions are strong in the neighborhoods, it makes it easier to monitor children's education and protect their rights. But, unfortunately, people living in apartments in high-rise buildings sometimes do not even know each other. They don't care what the neighborhood kids are doing here. They close their doors and show indifference as if they know that crime is being committed in the area, even in their basements. This is one of the problems that plagues all of us.

2. It is necessary to form an accurate database of children aged 7 to 18 in the neighborhoods in cooperation with families and schools. This information should include records of the child's living conditions, health, behavior, which school he/she attends, and attendance. Because those in charge, who notice the child's chronic absence from school, are able to take control in time.

3. To find out the reason for the neglect, failure to attend school and other negative situations of children with problems in single-parent families, and to always keep the family environment under control. If the child is completely neglected, if the parents do not fulfill their duties, then it is necessary to consider the issues of placing them in family orphanages.

4. It is very important to work with social psychologists and social pedagogues in ensuring community-family cooperation. Because every parent loves their child, parents don't like saying "your child is bad" when the child commits a crime. In such cases, a correct psycho-pedagogical approach applied to both the parents and the child is needed.

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